

TABLE BANKING CONTRIBUTION ON SOCIO- ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT OF HOUSEHOLDS IN TURKANA COUNTY, KENYA

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Abstract: Table banking is a concept that has gained popularity in the recent past in Kenya. The aim of this kind of informal banking is to enhance the socio-economic status of citizens particularly those from poor areas of the country. However, measuring and tracking changes in the levels of socio-empowerment of households through table banking not yet well established, although it's becoming popular among women groups in Kenya. The main objective of this study was to determine the contributions of table banking to socio-economic empowerment of households in Turkana County, Kenya. The specific objectives was: to assess the influence of table banking awareness on socio-economic empowerment of households, The study is guided by group joint liability theory, capability theory and Social Capital theory. The study adopted the descriptive survey design where data was collected by use of interviews and questionnaires to get primary data. Secondary data was used to validate the primary data. The study involved a sample of 398 members drawn using simple random sampling from a population of 67,500 Table banking members from Kalobeyei and Kakuma- Turkana West Sub-County. A total of 398 questionnaires were administered, this means the response rate was 97.0%. Furthermore, a regression equation model was developed to test the relationships between variables. From the findings, the variables respectively indicated their positive relationship. Therefore, the study exhibited a very strong, positive and significant relationship statistically between table banking and socio-economic empowerment of households. From the findings, the study has been observed that continuous and in-depth training of all table banking groups to enhance their skills especially related to financial management and presentation of the groups. The study also recommends that key stakeholders and both National and County government should consider to seek ways of empowering households with other socio-economic activities and programmes to boost their daily financial access. The study also recommends the government, table banking groups and other stakeholders involved in women empowerment should evaluate and improve table banking services in Kenya. Credits accessed in table banking group should be given clarity on repayment schedule and periods together with interest rate charged on credit. Lastly the several upcoming studies should be done to extract more information on relationship between table banking practice and engagement of households in business (small enterprises).

Keywords: Table Banking, Women Empowerment, Table Banking Awareness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Empowerment is critical to achievement of sustainable development and financial sustainability of a given community or a country. According to Kumar (2009), financial sustainability mainly focuses on the need to ensure information sharing, restoration and participation of people as key building blocks to ensure countries are supported to achieve their human development milestones. The concept of empowerment increases strength in diverse spheres of development, a process in which an individual or group gains independence, control and power over what happens in their lives (Amy C. Evans 2022). The benefits of empowerment of a community are defined by gender, location and access to development opportunities (IMF, 2013)). To empower means a broader understanding of the need for inclusion of the marginalized in the community.

World Bank (2012) defines empowerment as the process of enhancing the capacity of the individuals or groups to make decisions and act upon transforming those decisions, actions and outcomes towards a good course. However, a lot of emphasis is on the importance of empowerment in improving the well-being of especially women and the plight of marginalized people who are not in a better position to have self-sufficiency and self-confidence as a result of opportunities denied (World Bank, 2012). Kabeer (2001), links empowerment with economic empowerment, which combines the concepts of empowerment and economic advancement. Several approaches have been adopted to promote economic empowerment in order to help disadvantaged people in the society particularly women to succeed and advance in the marketplace. According to Kabeer (2001), these approaches recognize that economic empowerment is intertwined with social and cultural factors that limit households, especially women's ability to interact with and benefit from financial gains.

Socio-economic empowerment on the hand is the process of liberating people and communities from cycles of poverty and assigned social roles and giving them the resources, employment, education, health services to raise their and their communities social and economic opportunities. This process is meant to level the playing field and give disadvantaged people and communities the opportunity to take control of their lives and their future (Amy C. Evans 2022). Amy C. Evans (2022), posits that there are several examples of social-economic empowerment and can be find all over the world from local grass-roots organization to non-government agencies and on up to the United Nations. Many programs target women who traditionally earn less than men and are limited to specified gender roles within their societies as they are often perceived as the link to a household's health and to her community. They also have influence on the family and by extension their community. Empowering women especially through provision of skills and teaching them to realize their potential impacts on the socio-economic conditions not only to their households but in the communities, they live in.

Calyssa Burke (2020) points out table banking practice as one strategy of empowering households through women as its forefronts women as leaders of their own groups as men cannot hold leadership positions as the overall participation rate of table banking members is 70% female especially in Kenya. She added that, the process allows women to participate in accessing and contributing to the distribution of loans without having to qualify for loans by the agency of established banking associations. It continues to be an incentive for women to build their financial base and to start enterprises regardless of their literacy level. Consequently, the groups diversify their activities and go beyond financing household activities to grow into small business creation through saving, borrowing their own accumulated money and repaying it at some interest (Tembo Kenya, 2012). Further, Table banking does not require formal collateral or guarantees. It guarantees payment through group lending, saving, and alternative forms of collateral.

According to Akinrinola & Mafimisebi (2019), the sustainability of table banking groups is very vital for economic growth of any country because it is an excellent channel through which credit facilities can be granted to small business especially those in rural areas. The level of awareness of this group has enabled them to offer affordable loans, but they also make it for the members to guarantee one another. The level of Education by the group members creates awareness is disseminated by agents to members of groups to enable the latter get skills on the mobilization of savings and funds to boost their lending fund. Although the unbanked rural women entrepreneurs participate in savings support groups, their business growth is hampered by negative cultures, gender discrimination, and poverty (Aghion, Armendáriz, & Morduch, 2017). A group management characteristic is the act of guiding or influencing people to accomplish set goals or objectives (Ivancevich & Donnelly, 2016). Groups, irrespective of structure or foundation, are established to accomplish crucial objectives difficult to attain individually. Globally, there has been a massive. Most of the world's poorest people are women (Murgon & Lumwamu, 2014). Global Report (2019) observed that, globally, there has been a massive growth in the alternative credit arrangements and financial accessibility especially in the informal savings sector to empower people financially. More than 70 percent of the people in the emerging markets do not have a bank account and have come up with their own ways to save

money despite the aggressive marketing in the formal banking sector. Most of the people have formed informal saving groups and with their own set rules through constitution to govern the groups.

The origin of table banking can be traced from early civilization when money was exchanged at tables known as “Trapezes” which was first identified in Greece when ancient banking practices were conducted (Lin, 2016). During the ancient practice of table banking, money collectors received and documented amounts deposited by individuals and then borrowed to members of the solidarity group. As a participatory action process, table banking mediates between entrepreneurial intent for implementation and achievement of critical economic empowerment outcomes. Thus, the participatory action process is enhanced through shared information and acquisition of knowledge with which people work to gain mastery of skills to promote equity and improve the quality of life (Khandker, 2017). The people consider informal saving groups more accessible than the formal banks and financial institutions as they are keener in the provision of financial services to low incomers with the aim of empowering themselves economically (European Commission, 2018). According to Frey & Jegan(2019), socio-economic empowerment is the ability of the historically disadvantaged to engage in economic activities that benefit both the Individual and the broader society. Emphasis has been laid on adoption of entrepreneurship with indications pointing at its pivotal role in motivating sustainable livelihoods and lifestyle change across the globe. The cost of credit however, obstructs the unbanked poor to gain access to suitable financing services essential for them to initiate enterprise start-ups (Aguilar, 2006).

According to GEM (2012), women constituted the bigger segment of the world’s poor who are the most affected by ineligibility to access to available financing services and become entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship targets reduction of inequality in income distribution at household level and opportunity creation for employment for the poor. According to the Global Report on Food Crises 2018 it estimates that at least 25 percent of Kenya’s population is food insecure as a result of dry weather. As more women take ownership of land, they will be able to use their harvest as food to feed their households or as a means of income which will enable them to buy what they do not have at home, making their families food secure. Accessing savings services and small loans through Table banking, women acquire income that enable them to meet their basic household consumption needs rather than accruing significant debt which they could be unable to repay. When they borrow through Table banking, loan sizes are generally small and manageable depending on individual’s savings. Table banking is becoming popular with women groups in rural areas. It attempts to overcome the difficulties women face in accessing finances by having women groups pool their savings in order to have a source of lending funds (Murthi, 2019).

In Africa, Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs) provide valuable services to the poor, they are most successful in economically dynamic urban areas, where borrowing requirements are high and the costs of reaching clients is low. In contrast, most of the people in Africa live in rural areas and do not readily access finances or credit facilities. There is still a very large gap between the needs for financial services and the ability of MFIs to provide these services, especially to rural women. In addition, there is a gap between the products that MFIs offer and those that are needed by the women (World Economic Forum, 2019). African women constitute the majority of the continent’s population they however lag behind compared to men in many aspects. In most African countries, access to financial services like banking is lacking for many poor people. The situation is worse in rural areas where “most poor people especially women have neither the assets nor the skills to interact with formal finance institutions” (World Bank, 2005). Men and women are engaged in various productive economic activities in several sectors of the economic such as agriculture, livestock production and other socio-economic activities like small trade, food processing and handicrafts (Moll, 2005). However, despite the pool of money, they have collectively; they have less access to financial or banking services. There are also several opportunities available for the household to realize their capabilities. The opportunities include: increasing skills and access to productive resources, improving the enabling and institutional environments, and assisting women in their ability to make and act upon decisions in order to benefit from economic growth and development.

Marti and Mair (2009) state that, the failure of specialized financial institutions to address and meet the credit needs of the very poor entrepreneurs and women in particular has resulted in the popularity of informal groups such as table banking in most of the developing countries. Table banking is one of the ways that have been used to enable marginalized people, especially women to access financial services and support their participation in the economic sphere. According to Brannen (2010) table banking occurs when members of a group pool their savings together and borrow immediately from those savings on the table for a short period or for a long period, mostly a period of 1 to 3 months. Ahlen (2012) posits that table banking takes a model of the Grameen Bank of Bangladesh and the village savings and loan schemes (VSLs) of Zanzibar.

It has remained popular in most parts of Africa. Lack of socio-economic empowerment not only affects development of the affected areas but directly depletes the livelihoods of millions of Kenyans who are disadvantaged relative to accessibility of financial services from the mainstream institutions. Poverty and illiteracy still remain the greatest challenge to Kenyans, especially the rural folk. According to Limobk (2018), poverty level especially among Kenyan women currently stands at 25 percent. The Kenya government in 1999 launched the National Poverty Eradication Plan (NPEP) to provide a policy direction for enhancing partnerships with the relevant agencies and to mobilize resources to support in the fight against poverty. The plan was developed in response to global concerns on poverty (United Nations, 1995).

The summit set the goal of reducing poverty by half by 2015. A key resolution adopted was for participating member states to develop comprehensive planning and budgeting framework for making the goal a reality. The Government therefore, established the Poverty Eradication Commission through the Kenya Gazette in April 1999, to spearhead the fight against poverty and oversee the implementation of the National Poverty Eradication Plan (1999-2015) (GoK, 2000). The Commission had 14 specific mandates to execute, including advocacy for pro-poor policies and programmes; coordination, monitoring and poverty eradication initiatives and identification and piloting of best strategies to alleviate poverty. Poverty Eradication Commission (PEC) under the former Ministry of Planning and Vision 2030, targeting Millennium Development Goal (MDG) 1 on eradicating abject poverty, especially in rural settings in Kenya initiated table banking. The re-launch of table banking aimed at helping rural women access funds for investments in income generating projects (Kanyi 2014), the system has benefitted over 13 counties (Abuga 2014). Action Aid international Kenya also introduced table banking in Eastern Kenya through a project that aimed at supporting alternative livelihoods for people that are mostly affected by climate changes, banditry and other calamities (Kenya, Ministry of planning and National Development, 2016). About 97% of table banking members in Kenya are women. According to Njuguna (2017), table banking follows the same concept as merry-go-round but, for the former money contributed by members is given to members as loans which they pay back in the following meeting with an interest which is ploughed back into group savings.

In Kenya, the Women Enterprise Fund (WEF) was initiated to foster wealth distribution across various social groups through MSMEs projects (Shah, 2013; WEP, 2009). Due to its lean success, inclination towards community-led self-financing emerged. Table banking was first piloted in Gatanga and Bondo constituencies in 1999. The results were very impressive but the government did not continue with the roll out thereafter but was later on in 2004 improved to provide knowledge on its pros and cons. Basing on success-stories from the pilot projects, the Kenyan Government in 2005, resolved to officially launched table banking to reinforce its commitment to the women's economic empowerment agenda. Women groups also adopted the Table banking concept and since then there has been an ever-rising demand in various parts of the country especially in rural areas where it has spread over to forty-three counties (JOYWO, 2015). The rise in popularity of table banking has contributed to over 400 table banking groups in Nairobi alone (Joywo- Joyful Women Kenya Organization). Overall, table banking in Kenya has grown in value significantly, with groups across Kenya contributing the circulation of about country circulate approximately 60-80 million Kenya shillings (\$793,259.30-1,057,679) circulating monthly

Table banking has helped in economic empowerment as a saving and loaning scheme. It has given women, who were once totally dependent on their husbands for everything the ability to support their families as well. Women in Northern Uganda have learnt from Kenya, ladies who have not saved before have an opportunity to bring money that they have earned, saved and then use it to further their own sustainability (Judith, 2018).

Uptake of table banking since 2015 has been on the rise in some areas of Turkana County and especially in Turkana West Sub- County that has also gotten support from most of the NGOs operating in the area (NGO-led table banking groups. Through the benefits gained from table banking, the families are able to facilitate basic needs for their families and also the retention of their children in school, as well as meeting other family obligations and responsibilities like paying for medical services and expanding businesses that increase household income. There were also key projects mentioned that women have been empowered through table banking to engage in other activities like basketry, mat making, market linkages, livestock production- value addition, and marketing of farming products like maize, sorghum and fruits (Hon Joyce MP, Turkana County 2015).

According to Citizens (2021), table banking has been identified as having the potential to make a difference in the lives of poor women in Turkana. Table banking can be a game changer in financial empowerment of women in Turkana Country, enabling women to reap the benefits of financial autonomy. The opportunity provided banking has led to changing of

financial fortunes for women, Low-income households often encounter limited access to banking accounts or services to meet their working, investment needs and face high costs for transacting basic financial services through alternative financial service providers. As a result of lack of financial inclusion, especially related to where institutions that exist do not have services available and accessible especially to women, households find it more difficult to save and plan financially for the future. The policy and institutional arrangements in Kenya have been strengthened to promote women's participation in developments spearheaded by the ministry of devolution. Kenya National Bureau Statistics (KNBS report in 2021) revealed that, Turkana County remains one of the poorest communities with an absolute poverty level that is still high at 79.5 percent compared to national level, despite the coming of devolution. Women also still face cultural prejudices, domestic violence and economic alienation, which have serious implications on their health and economic status (UNDP, 2010).

Women low rates of land, asset ownership and residual lack of collateral limits them also to acquire capital to enhance their livelihood. Table banking has emerged as a sustainable avenue for bridging the gaps and enhancing socio-economic empowerment of women through flexible predictable long term access to savings and loans. Thus a significant understanding of table banking influence on awareness, financial accessibility, household participation, credit management risks and resources is also required for women to acquire independence in decision making which is critical for enhancing socio-economic status of households through women. Table banking has become a viable alternative financier of unbanked women from low-income households across Kenya, has seen women engagement in financial activities and randomly reported positively impacted on community members livelihood improvement. In Turkana County, there are a number of Table banking groups both NGO and individual led and mostly operated by women. This was first introduced in 2015 and although it has emerged as a strategy to bridge the gap of women accessing financial services and being accessible to savings and loan, its contribution to socio-economic empowerment of households through women is yet to be realized as fully envisaged. This study seeks to assess the influence of table banking awareness on socio-economic empowerment of households in Turkana County, Kenya

2. AWARENESS OF TABLE BANKING AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT OF HOUSEHOLDS

According to Mohindra (2019), table banking meetings open up a space for marginalized people in the community, especially women, to not only engage in financial activities, but also as safe space and a place of discussion. Through regular meetings, women become more comfortable in sharing their ideas, and learn to speak up for themselves and for each other. In turn, they begin to increase their voice outside of table banking's, in private and public domains creating a political autonomy for themselves. This voice may be used both within the household, to have more control over household decisions, positively impacting on the wellbeing of the family, or by participating in public debates and forums, potentially impacting on the formation of public health programs, services, and policies. Thus, presenting the importance of members of table banking groups to be meeting on a weekly basis.

Training is an important asset to an individual since it gives the necessary skills required to run a business. Stevenson and St-Onge (2019) observes that, proper accounting in any enterprise helps one to know what is going on as far as the business is concerned. In addition, Entrepreneurial, management, and technical training is very important to enterprise development and widening one's scope of doing things. The processes of table banking formation and training are critical stages for stability of the group. Training includes teaching rules and regulations, governing table banking procedures and administrative requirements, maintenance of book of accounts, rules for internal lending and repayment of loans, keeping the group fund intact. There are many governmental, private, and non-governmental agencies professing to offer training in areas such as starting a business, continuing its existence, and expanding it, yet very few female entrepreneurs have access to such according to Saluja, (2019). In explaining the importance of training and utilizing the knowledge women already have, Yunus, (2019), states that, there is need to train more women in group dynamics and team building strategies, record keeping, leadership skills, monitoring and evaluation of projects as well as proposal writing, including grants and business plans (Kane, Walsh and Nelson, 2018).

Kane et al (2020) further noted that the immediate social and economic environment experienced at the household level can be linked to a trend that makes most women groups struggle to operate their businesses efficiently. So, efforts must be made to strengthen women groups' management and logistical capacity (Herz, 2019). In addition, Jivetti and Edwards (2019), recommend that table banking members should be provided with training in the development of business plans and guidance

on how best to avoid redundancy or undue duplication of income generating activities and projects. The literature shows that there is little research, which has been done on the influence of table banking in enhancing socio economic status of households. Furthermore, literature has shown very little concerning the cost of accessing finance in the informal sector and the specific effects of table banking in enhancing socio economic status of households. The relationships between the table banking loans and personal development of individual entrepreneurs have not been as well exhausted. Concerning that, this study intends to explore the contribution table banking on socio economic status of households, a survey of Turkana West Sub County.

3. METHOD

A descriptive survey research design was employed with a target population of 2,700 registered table banking households from the Turkana County in Turkana West Sub-County (Kalobeyei and Kakuma wards). The data collection instrument was questionnaires both closed and open ended. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the research instrument. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. Data collected using questionnaires was entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software. In addition, inferential statistics that include Analysis of variance, Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis was used establishing the nature and extent of relationship between variables. To ascertain the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, a regression model was used.

4. DISCUSSION

The descriptive statistics results of table banking awareness on socio-economic empowerment of households in Turkana County, Kenya are shown in Table 4.1. According to the results, 63.6% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that table banking meetings open up a space for marginalized people in the community, especially women, to not only engage in financial activities, but also as a place of discussion. This statement had a relatively high mean score of 3.6186 indicating that the majority of the respondents agreed with it. Additionally, 88.1% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that Through regular meetings, women become more comfortable in sharing their ideas, and learn to speak up for themselves and for each other. This indicated that there was a high level of affirmation by the respondents which was reinforced by the high mean score of 4.2034.

The results also showed that 83.1% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that there should be Authority and Regulatory Framework for clarity of rules and regulations that guide daily activities. This statement had a mean score of 4.4237 indicating a very high affirmation by the respondents and agreeing with it. Further, only 41.5% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed while 30.5% were neutral towards the assertion that attending groups meetings are essential for the sustainability of table banking. This high level of uncertainty was also reflected in the mean of 3.3644.

According to the results, 70.3% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that Regular capacity buildings and training are essential for table banking. This statement had a mean score of 3.9322 indicating a high level of agreement. Lastly, 72.9% of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that Table banking awareness is highly emphasized as group participation enhances socio economic empowerment. This was an indicator of the affirmation by most of the respondents which was supported by the high mean score of 3.8305. A review of the standard deviations of the statements showed that all the standard deviations ranged between 0.76691 and 1.12216 indicating a low variation between each response and the mean responses.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of Table Banking Awareness

Statements on table banking awareness	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean	Std. Deviation
Table banking meetings open up a space for marginalized people in the community, especially women, to not only engage in financial activities, but also as a place of discussion.	0.0%	19.5%	16.9%	45.8%	17.8%	3.6186	0.99503

Through regular meetings, women become more comfortable in sharing their ideas, and learn to speak up for themselves and for each other.	0.0%	6.0%	5.9%	50.0%	38.1%	4.2034	0.80127
There should be Authority and Regulatory Framework for clarity of rules and regulations that guide daily activities.	0.0%	0.0%	16.9%	23.8%	59.3%	4.4237	.76691
Attending groups meetings are essential for the sustainability of table banking.	0.0%	28.0%	30.5%	18.6%	22.9%	3.3644	1.12216
Regular capacity buildings and training are essential for table banking	0.0%	0.0%	29.7%	47.4%	22.9%	3.9322	0.72476
Table banking awareness is highly emphasized as group participation enhances socio economic empowerment	0.0%	10.2%	16.9%	52.5%	20.4%	3.8305	0.87026

4.1 Inferential Statistics

4.1.1 Pearson Correlation Coefficient Analysis

According to Benesty, Chen, Huang and Cohen (2009), Pearson correlation coefficient refers to the extent to which two or more variables have a linear association. The Pearson correlation coefficients of this study are illustrated in Table 4.10. According to the results, the four independent variables, financial accessibility, table banking awareness, group participation, and credit risk management strategies had positive correlations of $r = 0.746$, $r = 0.791$, $r = 0.865$ and $r = 0.777$, respectively with the dependent variable, socio-economic empowerment of households in Turkana County, Kenya. a change in table banking awareness by one unit will lead to a corresponding change of 0.791 in socio-economic empowerment of households in Turkana County, Kenya;

Further, an assessment of the p-values showed that all the independent variable had p-values that were below 0.05 indicating that there a statistically significant relationship between all of them and the dependent variable. This affirmed that in instances where there are confidence intervals of 95%, p-values are supposed to be below 0.05 so that the observed differences between groups are not likely to be down to chance and, as such, statistically significant.

Table 4.2: Pearson Correlation Coefficients

		Table banking awareness	socio-economic empowerment of households
	Pearson Correlation	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
Table banking awareness	N	390	
	Pearson Correlation	.791*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.039	
socio-economic empowerment of households	N	390	390

4.1.2 Multiple Regression Analysis

Regression is a statistical technique that deals with the determination of linkages between one or more independent variables and a dependent variable by fitting a line of best fit through a series of observations (Mooi & Startstedt, 2014). The summary of the study's multiple regression model is presented in Table 4.11. These results show that the R Square value for all the variables was 0.714 indicating that the model explained 71.4% of any changes in the dependent variable, socio-economic empowerment of households whenever there is a one percent change in the independent variables. This means that the model managed to reach the 0.7 threshold for significance of the R Square value as recommended by Hamilton, Ghert and Simpson (2015). This demonstrates a fairly strong goodness-of-fit of the regression model.

Table 4.3: Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.848 ^a	.714	.682	.32978

a. Predictors: (Constant), Table Banking Awareness,

4.1.3 Analysis of Variance

Sawyer (2009) affirmed that the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is a statistical procedure that attempts to find out existing differences between experimental group means in situations where there are one or more independent variable and a dependent variable. The results of the ANOVA of the study are presented in Table 4.12. The results indicate that the ANOVA F-test score, calculated value F_{cal} at 5% level of significance is equivalent to 24.836, which is greater than the F critical value (F_{crit}) of 2.45 indicating that there is a significant relationship between all the independent variables and the dependent variable of socio-economic empowerment of households. The p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 indicating that there is a statistically significant relationship between each of the independent variable and socio-economic empowerment of households in accordance with the recommendations of Kao and Green (2008). This demonstrates the goodness of fit of the model.

Table 4.4: Analysis of Variance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	10.804	1	2.701	24.836	.000 ^b
	Residual	22.289	389	.109		
1	Total	33.093	390			

a. Dependent Variable: socio-economic empowerment of households

b. Predictors: (Constant), table banking awareness,

4.1.4 Beta Coefficient Analysis

Beta Coefficients as unknown constants that are projected from the data which are connected to particular independent variables (Peterson & Brown, 2005). These coefficients enable the measurement of the size of change in an independent variable and the manner in which this affects the dependent variable when the rest of the independent variables are held constant. The results of the Beta Coefficients of the study variables are shown in Table 4.13. The values of the constants and coefficients enabled the generation of the following multiple regression model:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon \\
 &= 4.200 + 0.137X_1 + 0.582
 \end{aligned}$$

Where, Y refers to the dependent variable (socio-economic empowerment of households), X_1 refers to the table banking awareness.

According to the equation, taking all the independent variables to be zero, socio-economic empowerment of households will be a constant equivalent to 4.200. A review of the findings also shows that a unit increase in table banking awareness will lead to a 0.137 increase in socio-economic empowerment of households when all other independent variables are held constant.

Table 4.5: Beta Coefficients

Model	Coefficients				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	4.200	.582		7.213	.000
1 Table banking awareness	.137	.065	.193	2.113	.037

a. Dependent Variable: socio-economic empowerment of households

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion basing on the study findings, the study came up with the following conclusions; a unit increase in table banking awareness will lead to a 0.137 increase in socio-economic empowerment of households when all other independent variables are held constant. The study recommends that continuous engagement and in-depth training of all groups who have adopted table banking practice to continue enhancing their skills especially related to financial management and performance of the groups. There should be regular capacity buildings and training essential for table banking. The study also recommends that key stakeholders and both National and County government should consider to seek ways of empowering households with other socio-economic activities and programmes to boost their daily financial access. Table banking meetings should open up a space for marginalized people in the community, especially women, to not only engage in financial activities, but also as a place of discussion to sharing their ideas, and learn to speak up for themselves and for each other.

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